

Consensus framework to assess eligibility of genes and hereditary diseases for genetic therapy development

Author list

Emilio D.R.O. Harris-Mostert^{1,2,3#}, Annelot C.M. van Esbroeck^{1,2,3*#}, David Cheerie⁴, Kai Lee Yap⁵, Christiana Wang^{6,7}, Rosan L. Lechner^{1,2}, Nicole Nolen⁸, Danique Beijer^{9,10}, Gregory Costain^{4,11,12,13,14}, Andrea Dardis¹⁵, Alissa M. D'Gama^{16,17}, Sam Finlayson¹⁸, Charu Kaiwar¹⁹, Pengfei Liu^{6,20}, Jangsup Moon²¹, Ana Lisa Taylor Tavares^{22,23}, Ella F. Whittle^{24,25}, Haiyan Zhou^{24,25}, Nicola Brunetti-Pierri^{26,27,28}, Keri Callegari^{6,20}, Maya Chopra^{29,30,31}, Brian H.Y. Chung^{32,33}, Hormos Salimi Dafsari^{34,35}, Elena Gardella^{36,37}, Matthias Kettwig³⁸, Lucia Laugwitz³⁹, Alexandria Mansfield^{4,40}, Ryan M. Marks^{4,41}, Julian W. März^{42,43}, Maureen A. McCall^{44,45}, Elizabeth E. Palmer^{46,47}, Carlo Rinaldi⁴⁸, Rugilė Stankevičiūtė^{49,50}, Matias Wagner^{51,52,53}, Marlen C. Lauffer^{3,48,54*}, and on behalf of the N=1 Collaborative

Shared first authors

*Corresponding authors: a.vanesbroeck@erasmusmc.nl and marlen.lauffer@paediatrics.ox.ac.uk

Affiliations

1. Department of Clinical Genetics, Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam, The Netherlands
2. Erasmus MC Center of Expertise for Neurodevelopmental Disorders (ENCORE), Rotterdam, The Netherlands
3. Dutch Center for RNA Therapeutics, The Netherlands
4. Program in Genetics and Genome Biology, SickKids Research Institute, Toronto, ON, Canada
5. Department of Pathology & Laboratory Medicine, Ann & Robert H. Lurie Children's Hospital of Chicago, Department of Pathology Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine, Chicago, USA
6. Department of Molecular & Human Genetics, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, TX, USA
7. Genetics and Genomics Graduate Program, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, TX, USA
8. N=1 Collaborative, Somerville, USA
9. Division of Translational Genomics of Neurodegenerative Diseases, Hertie-Institute for Clinical Brain Research and Center of Neurology, University of Tübingen, Germany; German Center of Neurodegenerative Diseases (DZNE), Tübingen, Germany,
10. Center for Human Genetics and Genomic Medicine, Uniklinik RWTH Aachen, Aachen, Germany
11. Department of Molecular Genetics, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON, Canada (Ryan's 33)
12. Department of Paediatrics, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON, Canada
13. Division of Clinical and Metabolic Genetics, The Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, ON, Canada
14. The Centre for Applied Genomics, SickKids Research Institute, Toronto, ON, Canada.
15. Regional coordinator Center for Rare Diseases, University Hospital of Udine, Udine Italy
16. Division of Newborn Medicine, Department of Pediatrics, Boston Children's Hospital, Boston, MA, United States
17. Department of Pediatrics, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, United States
18. Department of Pediatrics, Seattle Children's Hospital, Seattle, WA, USA.
19. Clinical Molecular Geneticist, Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, Precision Diagnostics Laboratory, Children's Hospital Colorado, Aurora, USA.
20. Baylor Genetics, Houston, TX, USA
21. Rare Disease Center, Department of Genomic Medicine, Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul, Republic of Korea
22. Genomics England, London, UK

23. Department of Clinical Genetics, Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, Cambridge, Cambridgeshire
24. UK Platform for Nucleic Acid Therapies (UPNAT), London, United Kingdom
25. Genetics and Genomic Medicine Research and Teaching Department, Great Ormond Street Institute of Child Health, University College London, London, UK
26. Telethon Institute of Genetics and Medicine (TIGEM), Pozzuoli, Italy
27. Department of Translational Medicine, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy
28. Scuola Superiore Meridionale (SSM, School of Advanced Studies), Genomics and Experimental Medicine Program, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy
29. Department of Neurology, Boston Children's Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Longwood, MA, USA
30. Translational Neuroscience Center, Boston Children's Hospital, Longwood, MA, USA
31. Division of Genetics and Genomics, Boston Children's Hospital, Longwood, MA, USA
32. Department of Paediatrics and Adolescent Medicine, School of Clinical Medicine, Li Ka Shing Faculty of Medicine, The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, Hong Kong, China
33. Hong Kong Genome Institute, Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, China
34. Department of Pediatrics and Center for Rare Diseases, Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital Cologne, University of Cologne, Cologne, Germany
35. Max-Planck-Institute for Biology of Ageing, Cologne Excellence Cluster on Cellular Stress Responses in Aging Associated Diseases (CECAD), Cologne, Germany
36. Danish Epilepsy centre Filadelfia, EpiCARE member, Dianalund, Denmark
37. University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark
38. Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine, University Medical Center Göttingen, Georg August University, Göttingen, Germany.
39. University of Tübingen, Department of Neuropediatrics, Developmental Neurology and Social Pediatrics, Tübingen, Germany
40. Temerty Faculty of Medicine, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON, Canada
41. Department of Molecular Genetics, University of Toronto, Toronto, ON Canada
42. URPP Innovative Therapies in Rare Diseases (ITINERARE), University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland
43. Institute of Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland
44. Department of Ophthalmology & Visual Sciences; University of Louisville, School of Medicine, Louisville, USA
45. Department of Anatomical Sciences & Neurobiology; University of Louisville, School of Medicine, Louisville, USA
46. Rare Diseases NSW, Discipline of Paediatrics and Child Health, UNSW Sydney, NSW, Australia
47. Sydney Children's Hospitals Network, Randwick, NSW, Australia
48. Institute of Regenerative and Developmental Medicine, Department of Paediatrics, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK
49. Vilnius University, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius, Lithuania
50. Vilnius University Hospital Santaros Klinikos, Center for Medical Genetics, Vilnius, Lithuania
51. Institute of Human Genetics, TUM University Hospital, School of Medicine and Health, Munich, Germany
52. Institute of Neurogenomics, Helmholtz Zentrum München, Neuherberg, Germany
53. Division of Pediatric Neurology, Department of Pediatrics, Developmental Medicine and Social Pediatrics, Dr. von Hauner Children's Hospital, University Hospital, Ludwig Maximilian University Munich, Munich, Germany
54. Department of Human Genetics, Leiden University Medical Center, Leiden, The Netherlands

Graphical Abstract

Graphical abstract adapted from Cheerie *et al.* (2025) with permission.

Abstract

Rationale: Approximately 6-8% of the world's population is affected by a rare disease. While advances in genetic diagnostics have increased the identification of disease-causing variants, opportunities to develop targeted and effective treatments are still lacking for over 90% of affected individuals. To ensure more individuals can benefit from genetic therapy developments, it is crucial to carefully evaluate for which patients and patient groups they will be efficacious. Notably, not all genes and diseases are equally suited for genetic therapy development.

Methods: The Patient Identification Working Group of the N=1 Collaborative set out to develop a framework to assess the eligibility of monogenic disorders for genetic therapy development. Following initial drafting, the framework was reviewed by a team of international colleagues in a structured feedback round.

Results: The resulting framework is aimed at clinicians and researchers to provide practical guidance and support during the assessment of genes and diseases for genetic therapy development. It is divided into molecular, clinical, and practical considerations. We additionally provide example assessments, alongside a wide range of resources to support the assessment process.

Conclusion: Complementing the evaluation of variant eligibility and individual clinical presentation, this framework constitutes a core pillar of the therapeutic actionability assessment.

Introduction

Although around 6-8% of the world's population is affected by a rare disease, only 5% of rare diseases currently have an approved targeted therapy, not accounting for individuals receiving off-label use drugs, leaving most individuals diagnosed with a rare condition without a treatment option.¹ According to the Operational Description of Rare Diseases², a rare disease is a medical condition characterized by a specific pattern of clinical signs, symptoms, and findings that affects no more than 1 in 2,000 individuals. However, definitions of rarity remain heterogeneous across countries, with different prevalence thresholds still in use. Most rare diseases are of genetic origin and improvements in molecular genetic diagnosis enable definitive diagnoses in around 40% of affected individuals.³ Identification of the underlying genetic defects allows improved disease management and genetic counseling, but it also provides the foundation for the development of treatments that target these disorders at their molecular bases.

These genetic therapies include modalities such as gene replacement, gene editing, and RNA therapies. Importantly, because these modalities are designed around a genetic cause rather than a syndrome label, they can be extended from higher-prevalence disorders, such as spinal muscular atrophy and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, to ultra-rare and even single patient (N=1) indications - an area with disproportionately limited therapeutic options.⁴ By late 2025, over 80 patients globally have been treated with an N=1 genetic therapy for a monogenic disorder.⁵⁻⁹

However, genetic therapies are not equally appropriate for all rare diseases; suitability depends on multiple factors including, but not limited to, molecular cause of disease, disease stage and progression rate, target tissue(s), therapeutic window, suspected clinical benefit, and adequate clinical outcome measures.¹⁰ Furthermore, the range of treatable conditions continues to expand as new insights help overcome current challenges, such as earlier genetic diagnoses, efficacious delivery to target tissues or cells, and the determination of optimal therapeutic dosing.

Before undertaking therapy development for a broader patient population or tailored to an individual, it is crucial to evaluate if and what kind of genetic intervention is feasible for the specific genetic target and, if so, which modality is best suited to the genetic target and intended therapeutic objective. Although some guidance is available for assessing specific types of disorders for a specific genetic intervention (e.g., gene therapy for neurodevelopmental disorders, ASO therapies for neurological disorders, and ASO therapies for all disorders¹¹⁻¹³), no overarching framework for assessment of genes and hereditary diseases for genetic therapy development has been established to date. In this paper, we (the Patient Identification Working Group (PIWG) of the N=1 Collaborative (N1C)) aim to provide an overview of considerations to assist with the evaluation of genes and diseases as candidates for genetic therapeutic intervention.

The N1C (<https://www.n1collaborative.org/>) is a global initiative aimed at establishing best practices for developing ultra-rare "N=1/few" therapies.⁹ To promote

safe and equitable access for individuals living with a rare disease, the PIWG specifically focuses on providing guidance for identifying eligible (1) disease-causing DNA variants, (2) genes and hereditary diseases, and (3) individuals for genetic intervention.

Scope and Purpose

This framework is aimed at a broad range of stakeholders across the rare disease ecosystem, including clinicians, molecular diagnostic laboratories, academic researchers, and therapeutic developers in the biotechnology and pharmaceutical industries. The framework may also serve as guidance for interventional genetic therapy boards, which are increasingly being established across institutions worldwide to evaluate cases for genetic interventions. The different stakeholders are provided with the knowledge and understanding to support initial eligibility assessment of genes and diseases for *in vivo* and *ex vivo* genetic interventions (gene replacement, gene editing, and RNA therapies, including ASOs, small interfering RNAs (siRNAs), mRNA replacement therapy, and RNA editing).

The framework focuses on monogenic disorders caused by germline (likely) pathogenic variants. Although the outlined considerations may apply to genetic interventions for complex and/or non-Mendelian diseases, these are beyond the scope of this work in this iteration. Such conditions include disorders caused by somatic variations (e.g., somatic cancers), contiguous gene syndromes, chromosomal aberrations, aneuploidies, and others; and also comprise more complex disorders caused by unique mutational mechanisms, for example, via retrotransposon insertions which cannot easily be targeted by genetic interventions. In addition, alternative therapeutic modalities, like cell therapies, enzyme replacements, small molecules, or mRNA vaccines are excluded from this initial framework. Genetically modified cell therapies, however, are included in this framework, as they are an *ex vivo* genetic therapy.

The framework reflects our current knowledge and understanding of the field. Considering the rapid advances in genetic therapy development and delivery, we aim to update the framework over time. We further anticipate that domain-specific (groups of diseases) or disease/gene-specific frameworks will be necessary in the future to adequately nuance these considerations. Such disease- or gene-specific guidance will enable clinicians to reliably identify diagnosed individuals who may be suitable candidates for (individualized) therapeutic approaches.

Overall, the evaluation process to assess a case or consider a group of individuals for genetic intervention has multiple steps. This framework addresses one important step in this evaluation (see graphical abstract). The full evaluation process consists of assessing the eligibility of (likely) pathogenic, disease-causing variants for specific genetic interventions, the gene and disease as well as the individual's/patient cohort's clinical presentation. A consensus guideline for the evaluation of pathogenic genetic variants for ASO treatments has recently been established by the PIWG.¹⁴ Additional

consensus and expert recommendations for the evaluation of gene replacement and gene editing therapies are currently under development. Further, the individuals themselves or the patient population need to be considered, and their clinical presentation thoroughly evaluated. It is also relevant to consider the wishes and needs of the patient population regarding potential therapeutic development. The latter considerations are outside of the scope of this work.

Only after all three pillars – variant, gene, and patient - have been evaluated and discussed, can therapy development commence where applicable. For individualized therapies, the development can take from 6 months to years,^{5,15} depending on the therapeutic modality. In contrast, therapies intended for larger groups of patients historically take multiple years to decades to develop, although these timelines can be shortened for rare diseases.⁴

Methods

Framework development

The consensus framework was developed as a multisite effort with input from researchers and healthcare providers (clinicians, genetic counsellors, etc.) with different backgrounds and levels of expertise. Six members of the PIWG (E.H.-M., A.v.E., D.C., K.L.Y., C.W., M.C.L.) initially developed an outline of the framework which was reviewed and edited by an additional ten members of the working group. The core six members then set out to write the first draft of the framework including figures and examples. This first draft was reviewed by twelve members of the working group who provided feedback. This was followed by a structured round of feedback consisting of colleagues at different career stages and from various countries and institutions outside the PIWG. For the structured feedback round, we invited colleagues with prior expertise in genetic therapy development and assessment as well as colleagues without prior knowledge on the topic to obtain a variety of insights. For the structured feedback round, the reviewers were given a standardized questionnaire to fill in following the manuscript review (**Supplement 1**). Thirteen reviewers provided feedback using the questionnaire. Three reviewers additionally provided feedback and comments within the text directly, adding up to a total number of 16 reviewers providing feedback. Feedback was implemented by the core group, and the finalized manuscript was sent out for final approval from all co-authors prior to submission.

Example selection

The framework was applied to 14 example diseases using a standardized template that incorporates all sections outlined in the framework. The examples and template are provided in Supplement 2. This template can be used and adapted by researchers and health care providers to gain an initial overview and insight on the amenability of a given disease to therapeutic intervention.

The examples were selected to address a variety of disorders, covering generalized and individualized approaches, diseases associated with different pathomechanisms including loss-of-function (LoF), gain-of-function (GoF), and dominant negative (DN), as well as different inheritance patterns. We further opted for some well-known examples to illustrate how the framework applies to disorders where a therapy is already available, as well as examples where a genetic therapy is currently not an option to demonstrate the applicability of our framework in such cases.

Genetic therapies

Genetic therapies can target the DNA or RNA (**Figure 1**). Interventions at the DNA level are generally presumed to be long-lasting and cannot readily be withdrawn once delivered, while RNA modalities typically have transient effects and can be modulated or discontinued. That means the effects of RNA therapies wane over time and require repeated dosing to maintain the therapeutic effect.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of DNA- and RNA-based strategies with applicable pathomechanisms indicated per strategy. Created in BioRender. Van Esbroeck, A. (2026) <https://BioRender.com/nl444sm>

DNA targeting strategies include gene replacement and gene editing, which can be performed both *in vivo* and *ex vivo*.¹⁶ Gene replacement therapy introduces a functional copy of the affected gene. This can be achieved using a full-length copy or an engineered mini- or micro-gene encoding a minimal, yet still functional protein product.¹⁷ Gene replacement strategies are most suited for disorders caused by mono- and bi-allelic LoF variants,¹⁸ and can also be considered for disorders caused by DN variants

where the goal is to shift the ratio of mutant to wildtype protein towards more wildtype protein.¹⁹ In contrast, gene editing therapies install disease-ameliorating genetic alterations within the genome, primarily through the CRISPR system (e.g., base and prime editing). Its application is mainly focused on single-nucleotide variants or small indels, limiting the range of targetable variants. CRISPR-based technology is rapidly evolving, and strategies to target more complicated variants, like repeat-expansions, have been tested pre-clinically.²⁰⁻²²

At the RNA level, a broad variety of therapeutic interventions exist, including mRNA platforms, RNA editing, siRNAs, and ASOs. mRNA supplementation therapies are especially suitable in cases of bi- and mono-allelic LoF pathogenic variants and rely on administration of (chemically modified) mRNAs enabling protein expression.²³ RNA editing approaches correct disease-causing variants at the RNA level, e.g. through antisense RNA-guided adenosine deaminase acting on RNA (ADAR). RNA editing is theoretically suitable for most pathomechanisms, however, it is limited to promote specific edits – most notably A to G.²⁴ siRNAs are short, non-coding, double-stranded RNA molecules that can silence gene expression using the RNAi pathway via RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC). They are particularly useful to target GoF and/or DN variants.²⁵ Alternatively, gapmer ASOs can be applied in a similar fashion, and can also be used to downregulate antisense transcripts. Gapmer ASOs are single-stranded, chemically modified oligonucleotides that bind to (pre-)mRNA, leading to recruitment of RNase H and subsequent degradation of the target transcript.²⁶ ASOs can also provide different modes of action, depending on their chemical make-up and target sequence. Steric blocking ASOs can be used to modify the splicing process to correct aberrant splicing, to skip (in-frame) exons containing pathogenic variants, or to alter the stability of transcripts by modifying the untranslated regions.²⁷ Depending on the ASO strategy, different types of genetic variants and pathomechanisms can be addressed.²⁸

Framework

To guide the discussions and considerations around the eligibility assessment of a disease or gene for genetic intervention, we decided to split this framework into three sections containing molecular, clinical, and practical considerations.

While there is overlap, we defined these three areas for ease of readability and usability of this framework. Dividing the framework into three sections also has practical reasons: (1) the first section contains considerations around the molecular basis and molecular understanding/cause of the disease, (2) the clinical section is focused around the clinical presentations and disease manifestation in individuals diagnosed with the disease, (3) and the practical section contains considerations that should be made before a therapy development commences and can provide additional understanding of what might be technically possible but not yet clinically feasible.

We refrain from providing any suggestions on weighing the criteria and instead recommend that all criteria be considered in their entirety. However, certain criteria can be considered “knock-out” or “no-go” criteria that will prevent the development of a genetic therapy. For example, instances where a therapeutic technology cannot be delivered to the target tissue or where the therapeutic window is closed upon birth, and a prenatal intervention would have to be considered. That means we would recommend carefully determining the limitations of therapeutic development and assessing whether these can be overcome with current knowledge and technological possibilities.

We present a condensed version of the framework, containing a high-level overview of the different criteria to be assessed, as shown below (**Figure 2**), with an extended framework available in **Supplement 3**. All listed sections in the condensed workflow are discussed in-depth in the same order within the detailed framework, including recommendations for resources to obtain relevant information. Additionally, the framework was applied to a set of example diseases to illustrate its suitability for assessing genes and disease for genetic intervention. Examples are provided in **Supplement 2** in a standardized format reflecting the three sections and individual criteria outlined within the framework. A list of additionally recommended resources for use with the framework can be found in **Supplement 4**.

Overview of considerations for genetic therapy development

Figure 2. Framework overview and checklist of considerations for genetic therapy development. Overview is separated into the three sections outlined in this framework. Created in BioRender. Van Esbroeck, A. (2026) <https://BioRender.com/cgrjtli> "

Molecular considerations

Before considering the eligibility of a gene or disease for genetic intervention, robust evidence on the molecular diagnosis, the gene-disease association, the disease mechanism, and the dosage sensitivity of a given gene/protein is essential. In the case of DNA and RNA editing, the disease mechanism and dosage sensitivity can, in certain circumstances, be omitted or may not be an essential consideration for therapeutic development as these approaches aim to restore the wildtype sequence and act irrespective of the underlying pathomechanism.

- Molecular genetic diagnosis and gene-disease association

A definitive molecular diagnosis with knowledge of the (likely) pathogenic variant(s), the molecular pathways of the affected gene, and gene-disease association are required prior to therapy development. Gene-disease associations should be evaluated at the variant level, as different variants in the same gene can act through different mechanisms and thus result in different diseases. Conversely, variants in different genes can lead to the same disease, potentially acting in the same or an adjacent signaling pathway.²⁹ Furthermore, the molecular diagnosis should account for all clinical features present in the individual.

- Penetrance and expressivity

It is necessary to evaluate the penetrance, prevalence, and expressivity of the identified variant(s) and associated disorders to estimate how many individuals would benefit from therapeutic development, how much therapeutic development would benefit them, whether a pre-symptomatic treatment should be considered, and to guide discussions on the benefit-risk ratio.³⁰ This criterion mainly applies to generalized assessments.

- Pathomechanism

Understanding the pathomechanism (*i.e.*, LoF, GoF, DN, or mixed mechanism) of the genetic variant(s) is essential before therapeutic development commences to guide possible therapeutic approach(es).³¹

- Dosage sensitivity

Understanding dosage sensitivity of a gene is relevant for choosing the most appropriate therapeutic approach and can help in establishing the minimally required and maximally tolerated effect of up- and/or downregulation through genetic intervention.³² Whether a gene is associated with haploinsufficiency or

triplosensitivity should additionally be considered to determine possible therapeutic applications.

- Therapeutic approach

Suitable therapeutic strategies can be selected once the gene-disease association, pathomechanism, and dosage sensitivity of a gene are defined. Knockdown approaches are particularly suitable for GoF and DN variants. Upregulation and gene replacement strategies are mostly suitable for LoF, and in some cases, DN variants.²⁸ Gene and RNA editing strategies are fairly independent of the underlying pathomechanism.

Clinical considerations

Evaluating the clinical presentation and defining treatment goals are both key in assessing the therapeutic eligibility of a disease. These considerations include the typical age of diagnosis, the natural history of the disease, the affected tissues, the associated symptoms, and the therapeutic window of opportunity. Symptoms should be considered with respect to their effect on quality of life, treatability, and suitability as clinical outcome measures. Ultimately, the potential clinical benefit must be weighed against the risks of genetic intervention, including the treatment burden of the procedures needed for the delivery of the therapy.

- Natural history studies

Obtaining natural history data of rigorous and highly standardized quality is essential for overall therapeutic decision-making.³³ When natural history studies or registries are not available, case reports including comparable genotypes can be a valuable source for individualized developments, but might not be sufficient for clinical trial design. The overall disease presentation, *e.g.* incidence, severity, and progression rate, will guide how much natural history data is necessary to make therapeutic decisions.

- Target tissue and delivery feasibility

Cells, tissues and organ systems affected by the disease must be identified to determine target tissues. Distinctions should be made between the primary and secondary affected tissues.³⁴ Ideally, the primary affected tissue(s) is targeted, but in certain cases, genetic therapy targeting secondary tissue(s) may be effective to either directly treat the disease or slow disease progression. These considerations are closely linked to understanding available delivery mechanisms and the pharmacokinetics of the therapeutic approach. When the affected cells or tissues cannot be targeted by the genetic therapy of choice, the clinical benefit of only targeting the accessible tissues must be carefully

weighed.³⁵ Furthermore, any additional tissues that will be targeted (off-targets) and resulting effects in this tissue need to be considered.

- **Types of symptoms and clinical outcome measures**

The clinical presentation of the disorder is crucial in determining whether a disease is suitable for therapeutic development. Generally, symptoms should be reversible. In addition, these symptoms should be easily measurable (standardized and quantified in an objective, reproducible way; where possible supplied with measurements obtained in a home setting) and should lend themselves to establishing clinical outcome measures. A disease is a suitable target for therapeutic development if clinical outcome measures reflect meaningful clinical benefit(s) to patients and caregivers.

- **Therapeutic window of opportunity**

To achieve the best possible treatment outcomes, the therapeutic window of opportunity needs to be defined, and therapy should be initiated within this time-frame.

This window depends on disease onset, disease stages, and progression rate. For fast-progressing diseases, especially when developing individualized therapies, the therapy development process may surpass the therapeutic window of opportunity. For slow-progressing diseases or those with a staged progression, it may take years to determine therapeutic benefit.³⁶ Additionally, understanding the different stages in the natural history of a disease, including their manifestation and duration, is relevant to determine at which point(s) a therapeutic benefit can be expected. Disease stage considerations are particularly relevant to assess eligibility for individualized therapy.

- **Therapeutic benefit and risk**

The risks and potential benefits of genetic intervention must be carefully considered. Many genetic interventions, especially individualized treatments, are still in an experimental stage and therefore pose a higher risk compared to well-established treatments. Discussions at what point the benefits outweigh the risks to support a treatment should be made within an interdisciplinary team comprising clinicians, researchers, ethicists and the patient population. As we continue learning more about safety and efficacy profiles, it is important to recognize that the same treatment may have a different risk-benefit profile in the future as increased knowledge is obtained. Risk assessment also depends on the genetic intervention of choice, the route of administration, and the accompanying possibilities of off-target effects.

Practical considerations

Additional practical considerations should be taken before therapeutic development can commence. These considerations include examining currently available therapies,

determining whether the pre-clinical development of the therapy is feasible, and deciding whether a generalized or individualized therapy is the most suitable. The pragmatic distinction between what might seem theoretically possible versus what is clinically feasible is crucial.

- Available therapies

Having an overview of available genetic and non-genetic treatment options approved or in clinical trials, and an understanding whether any of the options would be suitable for the individual or patient group in question can prevent unnecessary therapy development. Alternatively, already available therapies can be used to bridge until more suitable and efficacious therapies are developed. Such an overview can be extended to off-label use or drug-repurposing, and therapies targeting pathways up- or downstream of the affected gene/protein. If no treatment options are currently available, a thorough literature review of what has previously been done or tried preclinically can help prevent redundant efforts and guide further development.

- Pre-clinical development necessities

When deciding to develop a genetic therapy for a gene or disease, it is necessary to determine whether suitable *in vivo* and or *in vitro* models are available or can be established.³⁷ Furthermore, it should be decided at what level (DNA, RNA, protein, pathway, etc.) the therapeutic benefit should be assessed. Next, it must be considered what preclinical readouts are possible, have already been established and developed, and what readouts are necessary during preclinical development.³⁸

- Individualized therapy vs. generalized therapy

Insight into the patient population that could potentially benefit from genetic therapy can help prioritize target genes/variants. Whether therapy is developed for an individual or for a generalized patient population affects how the above considerations should be prioritized.⁴ For individualized therapies, the focus lies on improving the quality of life of the affected individual, and time plays an important role in therapeutic feasibility. Generalized patient population treatments can create opportunities for intervention in diseases where individualized approaches cannot be developed within the required timeframe, e.g. for very fast-progressing diseases that require presymptomatic diagnosis/treatment initiation. Of course, a therapy that has initially been developed for an individual can later be made available for a patient population where suitable.

With these considerations, we provide a framework of the relevant criteria to aid in the prioritization of genes and hereditary diseases for genetic therapy development. This framework guides the identification of suitable therapeutic strategies that fit the disease

pathomechanisms. More detailed information about each consideration and recommendations for assessment tools can be found in the **supplemental materials**.

When using the framework, we recommend writing out the results from the considerations in the checklist in **Figure 2**, using the template provided in **Supplement 2**. To provide an example, we present in **Table 1** the considerations for spinal muscular atrophy, as it is a prime example of a disease for which a genetic intervention is clinically beneficial, and where therapeutic success of multiple different targeted therapies has clinically been proven in the past decade.

Table 1. Considerations of the framework applied to spinal muscular atrophy using the standardized template.

Disease	SMA type 1	OMIM	# 253300	Orphanet	140468
Gene	SMN1	GeneReviews	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1352/		
Molecular Criteria					
Gene-disease association (incl. Molecular Diagnosis, Disease Understanding, Penetrance & Expressivity)	SMA is caused by biallelic LoF variants in <i>SMN1</i> , with >95% variants of large genomic deletion. A second gene - <i>SMN2</i> – is almost identical to <i>SMN1</i> and produces SMN protein, albeit at much reduced levels due to a genetic variation which affects the pre-mRNA splicing of <i>SMN2</i> exon 7. <i>SMN2</i> exists in multiple copies, and the number of copies modifies the phenotype and disease severity in SMA patients. ³⁹ Here, we evaluate SMA type 1.				
Inheritance + Pathomechanism	Autosomal recessive LoF				
Dosage sensitivity	Suspected sensitivity for high SMN doses. ⁴⁰				
Therapeutic Approach	Upregulation via gene replacement or via the <i>SMN2</i> copy allele. In general, gene editing is not a suitable option as the most common variants are larger deletions that cannot be edited.				
Clinical Criteria					
Natural History Data	Well-described disease across all SMA types that are associated with the number of <i>SMN2</i> copies with plenty of natural history data.				
Symptoms + Outcome measures	Muscle weakness and atrophy secondary to loss of motor neurons. Preventing the loss of these motor neurons in the spinal cord with genetic therapy can also prevent the development of muscle phenotypes. Outcome measures include the halt of progression or gain of developmental milestones.				
Progression rate + Therapeutic Window	Progression rates depend on the SMA type. SMA type 1 is a rapidly progressive disease that, left untreated, leads to death during childhood (before age of 2 years). Narrow window of opportunity for these children.				
Affected tissue + Target tissues	Multisystemic disorder, main manifestation caused by degeneration of the lower motor neurons, target tissue is the spinal cord.				
Therapeutic Benefit + Risk	Severe disease manifestation with death in early childhood (SMA 1), which justifies development of genetic therapy despite potential side effects.				
Practical Criteria					
Available targeted therapies	Spinraza (nusinersen) – antisense oligonucleotide Zolgensma (onasemnogene abeparvovec-xioi) – gene replacement therapy Evrysdi (risdiplam) – small molecule, splicing modulator				
Preclinical development necessities	Multiple mouse models for different SMA types are available, as well as cellular models like iPSC-derived moto neurons.				

Individualized vs. Generalized	Given the number of patients born with the disease every year, as well as the narrow temporal window of opportunity, a generalized approach is recommended.
Outcome	
Suitable for generalized genetic therapy development. SMA is a prime example of a severely debilitating and progressive genetic disease affecting the nervous system. There is a narrow therapeutic window for type 1, which is why the disease is better suited for a generalized therapeutic approach. Given its unique genetics (<i>SMN1</i> and pseudogene <i>SMN2</i>), there were multiple opportunities to develop distinct genetic therapies, all with the aim of enhancing SMN protein levels.	

Throughout the entire decision-making process, all considerations should be evaluated within the context of the individual case. This assessment is ideally with a multidisciplinary team that includes experts in the clinical manifestation of the disease, preclinical therapy development, ethicists, and regulatory affairs where applicable, as well as representatives of the patient population and/or caretakers. As the field advances, these considerations are expected to change, potentially expanding to include genes and diseases not currently considered suitable for genetic therapy development.

Discussion

Due to the substantial advances in genetic diagnostics and their widespread implementation in clinical practice, there is a growing need for clear, pragmatic, and clinically applicable guidance to translate these diagnoses into potential (individualized) therapeutic strategies.⁴¹ To support this transition and provide guidance to clinicians and researchers on how to prioritize genes and diseases for genetic therapy developments, the PIWG of the N1C developed a framework outlining general considerations at the molecular, clinical, and practical level. By providing broadly applicable considerations, such as stating the needs to understand tissue targetability, we have generated an initial framework that can grow with this emerging field.

The criteria and considerations presented here reflect our current knowledge and understanding of assessing genes and diseases for therapeutic developments. Yet, this framework has been developed with the recognition that the field is rapidly evolving, with new delivery systems, emerging clinical technologies, advances in molecular diagnostics, and the expansion of newborn screening on the horizon. We envision that, in the future, disease- or disease-group-specific guidance will complement these general recommendations and provide clearer direction on more complex, disease-specific issues.

The overall therapeutic decision-making should always be made in a multidisciplinary setting, including clinicians, researchers, ethicists, and the patient population. This evaluation consists of evaluating the disease-causing variant and the specific clinical presentations of the individuals. While these considerations are outside

the scope of this framework, it is worth mentioning that this should include understanding of how the disease impacts the patient's quality of life, what emotional and physical toll the treatment might have, and whether the patient is in a condition to tolerate the treatment burden. Existing comorbidities need to be considered before treatment can start, and whether these comorbidities might be contraindicative to specific therapeutic interventions.

In this context, it will be relevant to determine what constitutes a successful therapy trial following development. Here, the multidisciplinary team will have to decide whether success is defined by a positive surrogate endpoint (e.g., reduction in seizure frequency) or by a meaningful final clinical effect (e.g., extension of life, full reintegration into society, etc.). This discussion should evolve around how to balance intermediate outcomes with long-term benefits.

Other considerations include ensuring that informed consent is in place or can be obtained; where applicable, ethical approval for a therapeutic development has been obtained, and the economic aspects of therapy development and clinical administration have been discussed. It is also important to determine whether the necessary research (pre-clinical development) and clinical (clinical outcome measures, administration, and follow-up) expertise is available, or whether additional expertise should be sought. Initiatives like the N1C aim to support and streamline these developments, provide expert advice where needed, and aid in connecting researchers and clinicians.

Additional caution should be paid to the fact that the therapeutic development for an individual diagnosed with a rare genetic disease is vastly different from considering whether a disease is, in general, eligible for therapeutic development.

Thus, the goals and intended outcomes of the therapeutic development process should be clearly defined, with realistic expectations regarding development timelines and clinical benefits.

In summary, with this framework, we provide a structured and practical resources for the evaluation of genes and hereditary diseases to aid with the transition from an era of genetic diagnosis to an era of genetic therapy.

Acknowledgements

We thank our colleagues from the ZonMW PSiDER Consortium, the Dutch Center for RNA Therapeutics, and the N=1 Collaborative for their support in the development of this framework. We are also grateful to the patients and families we regularly engage with, whose experiences and perspectives have informed and inspired this work.

Data Availability

All information is provided in the main manuscript and supplementary files.

Ethics Declaration

This manuscript does not involve original research with human participants, human biological samples, individual-level human data, or animal subjects.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: E.H.-M., A.v.E., D.C., K.Y., C.W., M.C.L.; Project administration: E.H.-M., A.v.E., M.C.L.; Methodology (structured feedback rounds): E.H.-M., M.C.L.; Resources: E.H.-M.; Visualization: A.v.E.; Writing-original draft: E.H.-M., A.v.E., D.C., K.Y., C.W., M.C.L.; Writing-review & editing: E.H.-M., A.v.E., D.C., K.Y., C.W., M.C.L., R.L., N.N., D.B., G.C., A.D., A.M.D., S.F., C.K., J.M., P.L., A.L.T.T., E.F.W., H.Z., N.B.P., K.C., M.C., B.H.Y.C., H.S.D., E.G., M.K., L.L., A.M., R.M.M., J.W.M., M.A.M., E.E.P., C.R., R.S., M.W.

Funding

E.H.-M, A.v.E., R.L. are funded on the project '*Tailored: Towards a human iPSC neuronal platform for neurodevelopmental disorder therapeutic discovery*' with project number 10250022110002 of the PSIDER research program, (partly) financed by the Dutch Organisation for knowledge and innovation in health, healthcare, and well-being (ZonMw). M.C.L. was funded by a Walter Benjamin Fellowship of the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft [DFG], project no. 521414448) and a Sectorplannen position from the Dutch government. M.C.L. is currently funded by the Department of Paediatrics at the University of Oxford. This work was supported by the MRC Centre of Research Excellence in Therapeutic Genomics (MR/Z504725/1). N.B.P. was supported by Fondazione Telethon ETS, and this study was generated in part within the European Reference Network on Rare Congenital Malformations and Rare Intellectual Disability (ERN-ITHACA). This work was supported by the European Union - Next Generation EU - NRRP M6C2 - Investment 2.1 Enhancement and strengthening of biomedical research in the NH (PNRR-MR1-2022-12376412, CUP61H22000130001 to N.B.P.). C.R. is supported by an MRC Fellowship (MR/Y009703/1). C.W. is supported by the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (U.S.A.) under award number F31NS145565. D.B. is supported by the Hertie-Network of Excellence in Clinical Neuroscience. The SickKids authors (D.C., G.C., A.M.) acknowledge funding from the Canadian Institutes of Health Research and the Azrieli Precision Child Health Platform. A.M. also receives salary support from Temerty Faculty of Medicine, University of Toronto, via the Graduate Diploma in Health Research Program. E.E.P. receives a

fellowship from the National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) [2021/GNT2008166]. A.M.D was supported by the Boston Children's Hospital Translational Research Program, a Boston Children's Hospital Office of Faculty Development/Basic & Clinical Translational Research Executive Committees Faculty Career Development Fellowship, and a Thrasher Research Fund Early Career Award. L.L. was supported by the Else Kröner-Fresenius Memorial Scholarship (grant no. 2025_EKMS.48) and the Else Kröner-Fresenius Re-entry Scholarship (grant no. 2025_EKSP.254). H.Z. and E.F.W. are supported by The UK Platform for Nucleic Acid Therapies (UPNAT). UPNAT is funded by the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) & the Medical Research Council (MR/Y008405/1 to H.Z.). M.W was supported by a Hertie Foundation fellowship (P1230037) and is currently supported by an Else Kröner Fellowship of Excellence (2025_EKES.12).

Conflicts of Interest

J.W.M reports consulting fees and speaker honoraria from Somagenetix AG, Boehringer Ingelheim Fonds, Treat-NMD, the Swiss Federal Office of Public Health, and INFRAS AG. E.E.P. is a medical and scientific board member for Rare Voices Australia. M.W. received speakers honoraria from Desitin and USB, served on advisory boards for Pharming Group and Stoke therapeutics and receives research funding from Novartis and Biogen.

Declaration of AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to assist with language editing and sentence restructuring. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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